

DISCOURSE INTERFERENCE IN THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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ANNOTATION

The article deals with the troubles of the language interference with-inside the system of the English language learning. The tendency to interference is stronger via way of means of interaction numerous languages and ends in a worry of the communication system. Practice teaching English as a foreign language in our country shows the want for a clean methodological employer the system of studying a foreign language, primarily based totally at the characteristics all languages studied by students. For exceptional student mastering a foreign language ought to recollect all viable linguistic problems primarily based totally on comparative evaluation in situations multilingualism so as to overcome interference. The article discusses the issues of interconnection of language competence and interconnection of language contacts, interference as well as their reflection in the discourse and communicative process.

Keywords: *interference, vocabulary, foreign language, native language.*

Language acquisition is one of the most important and fascinating aspects of human development. There are various subconscious aspects of language development such as metalinguistic, conscious, formal teaching of language and acquisition of the written system of language in both L1 and L2. Various language variables are involved in the language processes like phonology, vocabulary, morphology, syntax, paralinguistic, pragmatics and discourse. In order to provide success in cognitive

functioning as well as professional life of an individual, his/her first language acquisition must develop strongly in the early years.

One of the major obstacles in acquiring the second language is mother tongue or L1 interference especially in productive skills of speaking and writing. Mother tongue interference affects L2 learning as “language” is considered as a set of new habits while “learning” is considered as the establishment of habits.

Thus, language interference has attracted the attention of scientists for many years. These problems are the subject of dissertations of many scientists as ours. The importance of studying language interference is increasing due to the practical demand for this knowledge in the realities of the modern development of world science, culture, engineering and technology.

First of all, we try to analyze the definition of the phenomenon of “interference” given in the Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary. “Interference from the Latin “inter”- between each other, mutually and “ferio”- touching, strike– the interaction of language systems in the conditions of bilingualism, which develops either when contacts are in languages, or when an individual learns a foreign language and it is expressed in a deviation from the norm and system of the second language under the influence of the native.

However, there are different types of interference, such as, phonetic, semantic, lexical, grammar, spelling, stylistic, linguistic and regional studies, sociocultural interferences. Interestingly, there is not a specific type that is called discourse interference as it is studied within lexical, grammar and spelling. Nevertheless, Language specialists and teachers have long been interested in the study of discourse, whether written or spoken as a means of identifying the mental processes underlying learning. According to Agudo, one of the biggest challenges for the EFL teachers is the problem of motivating and teaching the students how to adapt their cultural thinking and use of foreign language as per the native speakers of that foreign language¹.

¹Agudo, J.D. “Native and non-native teachers in English language classrooms.” (2017)

The effect of the native language can be examined in the writings of an EFL learner and serves as the essential technique used by the EFL teacher to test the proficiency of the students. The prevailing literature claims that the speakers of the native language tend to transfer the arrangements from their native language to their usage of English. Nevertheless, this association between the mother tongue and discourse in a second language is not just encountered by all learners and it is common in Chinese students who are learning English¹. Richards and Schmidt define Interlingua errors as the outcome of language transfer affected by the native language of a learner. According to Zhu and Aryadoust language transfer is either positive or negative. A transfer is called positive if it is found justified because of the similar structure of the two languages or it may be unjustified due to the different structures of any two different styles². In addition, a typical mistake of Russian students is confusion in the word order of the English sentence. Students forget that in the affirmative English sentence must be subject, and in the affirmative sentence it always faces the predicate. If the words order in Russian is free “Я вчера играл в парке”, “В парке играл я вчера”, “Играл в парке вчера я”, then in English the word order is strictly fixed, and each member of the sentence has its own specific place: “I played in the garden yesterday” – the subject always faces the predicate, and in impersonal sentences you can't just use a verb or an adjective, like in Russian language.

To conclude, EFL learners face mother tongue interference when writing in English, the significant areas of error are subject-verb agreement, verb usage, word order and collocation. Rules of grammar and usage are at odds between native language and English, and it appears that lack of clarity and poor practice in writing work prevents the assimilation of these for them.

¹ Ahmed, F. “An Investigation of Writing Errors of Saudi EFL University Students at King Halif Un”. (2016).

² Zhu and Aryadoust, V. “An investigation of mother tongue differential item functioning in a high-stakes computerized academic reading test”. (2020).

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